

EFFECTS OF AROMATHERAPY ON POSTOPERATIVE NAUSEA AND VOMITING:

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

by

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Abstract

Post-operative nausea and vomiting (PONV) is one of the most common adverse reactions patients experience after a surgical procedure requiring anesthesia (Sizemore et al., 2022). On average, one-third of patients who undergo anesthesia experience PONV of varying severity (Sizemore et al., 2022). High-risk patients face an 80% chance of PONV (Sizemore et al., 2022). Further complications that can arise out of PONV include the patient's inability to tolerate elevated intrathoracic pressure, increased blood pressure, or increased heart rate (Sizemore et al., 2022). There are many factors preoperatively and intraoperatively that can increase the risk of PONV including the use of nitrous oxide, opioid administration for pain, and the duration of surgery (Jin et al., 2020). Other risk factors for postoperative nausea and vomiting include female gender, non-smoker, the use of opioids postoperatively, and history of motion sickness or PONV (Jin et al., 2020). Depending on the risk factors a patient has, the amount of antiemetics prescribed can be increased, which can therefore raise medical costs (Jin et al., 2020). Severe PONV can cause extended stays in post-anesthesia care units (PACU) and can cause an additional \$75 worth of treatment per patient (Jin et al., 2020; Trandel-Korenchuk et al., 2022). PONV is also linked with a delayed recovery process, and could potentially lead to increased morbidity and mortality of patients (Cao et al., 2017). The risks of prolonged antiemetic use include tolerance and possible sedation (Nowak et al., 2022). Antiemetics can pose potential side effects, most common being weakness, headaches, and dizziness (Cao et al., 2017). Therefore, non-pharmacological methods, such as aromatherapy, are preferred methods of PONV treatment to reduce the possibility of additional side effects.

The aim of this systematic review is to determine whether aromatherapy decreases PONV in patients who underwent anesthesia in surgery. Objectives include: Determining randomized

controlled trials that compare the effect of aromatherapy on PONV to a placebo; Creating a systematic review with a succinct accumulation of research findings to provide hospitals a resource to refer to when looking at the efficacy of aromatherapy and eventually adopt aromatherapy practices hospital-wide; Determining which aromatherapy scent is most effective in reducing PONV; Discovering strengths and limitations of studies published on the effects of aromatherapy on PONV. By completing a literature review, a synthesized conclusion can be made on the effectiveness of aromatherapy for PONV.

Effects of Aromatherapy on Post-Operative Nausea and Vomiting

A common side effect that occurs from anesthesia is postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV). Postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) is defined as an uncomfortable feeling of impending or active gastric reflux after surgery (Keikhaie et al., 2020). In the United States, up to 50 million surgeries occur annually, with approximately one-third of these patient experiencing PONV (Dobson, 2020; Sizemore et al., 2022). In these surgeries, PONV can increase a patient's costs by \$74 USD and length of stay in a post-anesthesia care unit (PACU) by 1 hour (Jin et al., 2020). Controlling PONV is imperative, as uncontrolled PONV can cause post-operative complications such as rupture of surgical closure (wound dehiscence), prolonged healing, pulmonary aspiration, electrolyte imbalances, and dehydration (Ahmadi et al., 2020; Hodge et al., 2014; Jin et al., 2020).

While medications like ondansetron, metoclopramide, or promethazine are often given in conjunction with anesthesia to prevent this outcome, PONV still occurs across all age groups (Keikhaie et al., 2020). Side effects of antiemetics can be plentiful, depending on the drug classification, and they can include lightheadedness, arrhythmias, and abnormal liver enzyme production (Whitley, 2022). A proposed non-pharmacological adjunct to medications for PONV is the use of aromatherapy after surgery. Aromatherapy can be a method to help reduce PONV and can be implemented before a provider's order for an antiemetic (Hauser et al., 2022). Current pharmacological treatment for PONV relief includes butyrophenones and dopamine receptor antagonists (Hauser et al., 2022). However, these medications can cause a plethora of potential side effects, including dry mouth, hypotension, and extrapyramidal reactions, including tardive dyskinesia (Hauser et al., 2022). The use of aromatherapy as a first-line adjunct therapy for PONV can help deter patients from experiencing additional side effects. Non-pharmacological treatment currently used for postoperative nausea and vomiting includes nausea relief bands,

acupressure, acupuncture, music, intraoperative oxygen inhalation, smelling isopropyl alcohol, and transcutaneous electrical stimulation (Cao et al., 2017; Hodge et al., 2014). Currently, there is no uniform non-pharmacological protocol for PONV used throughout hospitals in the United States.

To search for scholarly articles that fit the criteria of the research question, the Boolean operators used were “postoperative nausea and vomiting” AND “aromatherapy.” Inclusion criteria included the use of essential oil aromatherapy compared to a placebo, studies done post-operatively, all age groups, all surgery types, and the presence of PONV in patients undergoing the experimental treatment. The majority of studies were published in 2018 and after. Three studies included were dated as older than 2018; however, they were heavily cited in current research articles and compared aromatherapy efficacy over time (Anderson & Gross, 2004; Hodge et al., 2014; Hunt et al., 2013). Studies were excluded if they were not in English, did not have approval from an ethics board, were not compared to a placebo, and were solely preoperative or intraoperative studies. The search engines used were CINAHL, Google Scholar, and Pubmed.

Antiemetic Side Effects

Drug classes of commonly prescribed anti-nausea medications include the following: serotonin-receptor antagonists, glucocorticoids, anticholinergics, neurokinin receptor antagonists, dopamine receptor antagonists, butyrophenones, benzamides, cannabinoid therapy, and antihistamines (Hauser et al., 2022). The most severe potential side effects are in butyrophenones, including Haloperidol (Hadol) and Droperidol (Inapsine). Butyrophenones can cause a prolonged QTc interval, which can result in the fatal arrhythmia of Torsades de Pointes (Hauser et al., 2022). Dopamine receptor antagonists also have severe potential side effects of

extrapyramidal symptoms, including akathisia, tardive dyskinesia, and dystonia (Hauser et al., 2022).

Antiemetic medications also contain contraindications, posing potential additional adverse effects. Serotonin-receptor antagonists can cause potential serotonin syndrome if taken alongside selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors, monoamine oxidase inhibitors, and the tetracycline antidepressant mirtazapine (Hauser et al., 2022). The risk of potential side effects and contraindications requires closer monitoring of patients.

Pathophysiology

The sensation of nausea and vomiting is due to the trigger of the vomiting center from a multitude of pathways. The chemoreceptor trigger zone, vestibular system neuronal pathways, midbrain afferents, cerebral cortex, and gastrointestinal vagal mucosal pathways get stimulated via anesthetic mediations, triggering the vomiting center (Nagarekha et al., 2016). This trigger either ends in nausea or further stimulation of the visceral, somatic, and motor pathways that cause the vomiting reflex to occur (Nagarekha et al., 2016).

Aromatherapy works by activating the olfactory system by traveling to the olfactory bulb (Farrar & Farrar, 2020). The stimulus ascends to structures in the brain (amygdala and hippocampus) to release endorphins, causing an analgesic effect (Farrar & Farrar, 2020). Aromatherapy has also been shown to lower the parameters of pulse, blood pressure, and muscle tension, contributing to a relaxatory effect (Farrar & Farrar, 2020). Aromatherapy has also been linked to effectively decreasing rates of nausea and vomiting, however the exact mechanism of how is unknown (Farrar & Farrar, 2020).

Factors Influencing Postoperative Nausea and Vomiting

The type of surgery is one of the most significant factors contributing to the amount of postoperative nausea and vomiting experienced by the patient. There are higher incidences of PONV in gynecological, laparoscopic, and cholecystectomy procedures, and in procedures that last longer than 30 minutes (Chatterjee et al., 2011; Nagarekha et al., 2016). These results are compared to procedures in male patients, lasting less than 30 minutes, and that do not involve instillation of CO₂ into the peritoneal cavity (Chatterjee et al., 2011; Nagarekha et al., 2016). Gynecological surgeries have higher incidences, because of a combination of risk factors, including female gender and perioperative opioid use (Chatterjee et al., 2011). Laparoscopic procedures are camera-guided procedures done by inflating the abdomen with carbon dioxide. This inflation causes pressure on the vagus nerve, which can prompt a response from the nausea and vomiting center in the brain (Chatterjee et al., 2011). A cholecystectomy, or gallbladder removal surgery, is often done laparoscopically, resulting in the same vagal nerve stimulation pathway (Chatterjee et al., 2011). Secondly, the duration of the surgery also influences the amount of postoperative nausea and vomiting experienced, as longer surgeries are associated with higher rates of PONV (Chatterjee et al., 2011). Thirdly, the types of anesthetics also play a factor, as medications affect the rates of nausea and vomiting. Higher rates of postoperative nausea and vomiting are associated with nitrous oxide and ketamine, while lower rates are correlated with Propofol and Dilaudid (Nagarekha et al., 2016). Fourth, the use of opioids and ambulation is linked with higher rates of PONV (Nagarekha et al., 2016).

Results

A table of evidence (See Table 1) was made looking at a total of 13 articles that all experimented with the use of various aromatherapy scents on patients in different age groups after a variety of surgeries. The scents most effective in reducing PONV and eventually

decreasing the amount of antiemetic medications used were peppermint essential oils (Abril et al., 2019; Ahmadi et al., 2020; Anderson & Gross, 2004; Fearington et al., 2019; Maghami et al., 2020) and blend essential oils (Fearington et al., 2019; Hunt et al., 2013; Marsh et al., 2021; Norton et al., 2022; Trandel-Korenychuk et al., 2022).

Peppermint Aromatherapy

Peppermint essential oils were used in a variety of surgeries. These surgeries included cases that increase the risk and severity of PONV, such as laparoscopic, abdominal, and open heart (Abril et al., 2019; Ahmadi et al., 2020; Maghami et al., 2020). The study examining female adult patients undergoing laparoscopic surgeries used a four-point visual analog scale for patients to report their nausea levels before and after entering the post-anesthesia care unit (PACU) (Abril et al., 2019). Patients used a handheld sniffer with peppermint essential oil of only one concentration. No placebo was used in this study. Out of 35 patients smelling peppermint essential oil through a handheld sniffer, 73% of patients who used peppermint aromatherapy reported complete resolution of their nausea by the time of their discharge (Abril et al., 2019). 88% of patients who solely used aromatherapy and did not use antiemetics were those who experienced total resolution of their nausea throughout their PACU stay (Abril et al., 2019). The primary limitation of this study was the small sample size, which caused there to be no direct causal relationship between peppermint aromatherapy and PONV. Since no placebo was utilized, the results appeared to be significant, as the only comparison factor was patients who did not receive a sniffer and could not mimic the action of smelling aromatherapy.

Similarly, the study examining patients undergoing coronary artery bypass grafts was conducted in Iran and contained a sample size of 60 participants (Maghami et al., 2020). The experimental essential oil was 10% peppermint, and the placebo was distilled water, both were given as nebulizers. The average nausea severity in the control group was 2.12 times higher than

in the intervention group (Maghami et al., 2020). The duration of nausea was 2.32 times higher in the control group than in the peppermint intervention group (Maghami et al., 2020). 4 hours after extubation, the nausea duration, frequency, severity, and occurrence of vomiting were lower in the experimental group compared to the distilled water placebo group (Maghami et al., 2020).

The final study solely used peppermint oil and experimented with the effectiveness of 30% peppermint oil versus 10% peppermint oil in teen and adult patients undergoing abdominal surgery (Ahmadi et al., 2020). A nausea visual analog scale was used to assess the severity of nausea in patients. The essential oils were saturated onto a gauze pad and then given to patients to smell independently. The placebo in this study was distilled water colored with green food coloring to mimic the appearance of peppermint essential oil. The 10% and 30% peppermint oil successfully decreased nausea (Ahmadi et al., 2020). The 10% group experienced a decrease in nausea by 11.8%, and the 30% group experienced a decrease of 20.5%, compared to the placebo group, which experienced a decrease in nausea by 3.2% (Ahmadi et al., 2020).

An older article published in 2004 that was cited by four studies conducted within the past five years (Anderson & Gross) compared the effects of peppermint essential oil in adult patients undergoing outpatient surgery. A visual analog scale (VAS) was used where patients rated satisfaction of nausea reduction from zero to 100. This study established that age or surgery type does not significantly impact aromatherapy effects. It was determined that 20% of patients in the peppermint group requested emergency antiemetics after two minutes of receiving aromatherapy versus 8% of the placebo saline group. Peppermint essential oil was also found to be less effective than isopropyl alcohol, where 18% of participants requested emergency antiemetics. Both experimental groups required a higher percentage of antiemetics, deeming both groups statistically insignificant. Based on this study, peppermint and isopropyl alcohol aromatherapy do not reduce PONV compared to a placebo. The same size of the study was on

the smaller end, with 33 participants: 10 being in the peppermint group and 12 being in the placebo saline group. Overall patient satisfaction with nausea management graded on a visual analog scale was 86.3% for the peppermint group versus 83.7% for the saline group. This study also looked at ambulatory surgeries, which pose a lower risk of PONV. Experiments recreated after this study found contrasting results and have deemed peppermint aromatherapy as effective for PONV.

Similarly, a 2019 study (Farrington et al.) examined the effects of peppermint essential oil on same-day, short-stay surgeries, which are also considered to lower the risk of developing PONV. This study had a large sample size of 322 patients, of which 179 patients were in the control group that did not receive any aromatherapy. The experimental group had more participants with a history of PONV – 14% of participants compared to 4.5% of participants in the control group. Yet, the control group used more antiemetics (0.53 ± 0.85) than the experimental group (0.15 ± 0.47). A clear distinction between the various arms (peppermint, ginger, combination) was not made; however, it was established that PONV decreased in all experimental categories.

Blend Aromatherapy

Blend essential oils were also examined in six studies, all of which deemed blends to be effective in reducing PONV (Farrington et al., 2019; Hodge et al., 2014; Hunt et al., 2013; Marsh et al., 2021; Norton et al., 2022; Trandel-Korechuk et al., 2022). Blend scents examined included peppermint and ginger (Farrington et al., 2019), spearmint, peppermint, lavender, and ginger (QueaseEASE) (Hodge et al., 2014), ginger, spearmint, peppermint, and cardamom (Hunt et al., 2013), lavender, peppermint, ginger, and lemon (Marsh et al., 2021), spearmint, peppermint, lavender, and ginger (QueaseEASE) (Norton et al., 2022), and one study did not disclose which essential oils were in the blend (Trandel-Korechuk et al., 2022). The blend of

peppermint and ginger essential oil in a combination branded “QueaseEASE” contained an experimental sample size of 179 patients (Farrington et al., 2019). Again, there was no clear distinction in experimental categories in this study, so differentiation results based on essential oil utilized could impact determined effectiveness.

Looking at patients who underwent more invasive surgeries that require in-patient admission, when QueaseEASE blend aromatherapy was utilized, the patient’s nausea dropped 2 points out of a six-point scale in the experimental group, compared to the placebo group, which experienced a drop of 1.2 points (Hodge et al., 2014). It is also important to note that this table was a stronger study type, compared to other studies examined (Polit, 2018; See Table 1). The placebo and experimental groups had similar satisfaction with nausea treatment, with a score of 6.8-7.1 out of 10 on a Likert scale. This study showed that aromatherapy was effective but did not yield as high efficacy as other studies. This could indicate that the effectiveness of aromatherapy is contingent on the patient's age. No evidence was collected regarding which group required more antiemetics, which would have been a useful indicator regarding whether aromatherapy is an adequate deterrent to the need for aromatherapy.

Another study examined the effects of the same aromatherapy blend, QueaseEASE, except in less invasive outpatient surgeries, including eye surgeries and tonsillectomies (Norton et al., 2022). QueaseEASE was administered as a pod in a foil pack, which released a scent when the foil was peeled back. This study contained a sample of 31 pediatric patients and utilized the Baxter Animated Retching Faces (BARF) 6-point scale to rate nausea before and after the intervention. It was found that while BARF scores decreased in both male and female patients, there was a more significant decrease in BARF scores in male patients than in female patients. This finding is significant, as it could mean aromatherapy has better outcomes in specific populations. With a significant decrease in the BARF score by >2 points, 77.4% of patients in the

experimental group experienced a significant decrease in their BARF score. Additionally, it was found that 51.8% of patients continued using their aromatherapy pod at home. The limitation of this study was the lack of a placebo to measure aromatherapy results. This study utilized the same blend and yielded similar results to a study conducted on patients with planned post-operative in-patient admissions, meaning the scent blend is versatile for various surgeries and, therefore, anesthetics used (Hodge et al., 2014; Norton et al., 2022).

Blend aromatherapy was also effective in ambulatory surgeries requiring shorter recovery time (Hunt et al., 2013). In a study with a sample size of 300 patients separated into 4 groups, each with 75 patients, blend aromatherapy was the most effective scent in decreasing PONV. The participants in the blend group also received less emergency antiemetics than the placebo group. 82.4% of participants in the blend group reported lower amounts of PON. This study also examined ginger essential oil, which was more effective than the placebo, but blend aromatherapy decreased PON by 15.3% more than the ginger group. Another surgical category with a lower predisposition to PONV, lower extremity fracture repair, experienced similar findings regarding PONV reduction (Marsh et al., 2021). The control group used for this study had no aromatherapy being used. The sample size in this retrospective study was the largest among the studies examined, with 810 patients in 2019 and 886 patients in 2020. Key findings included a 21% decrease in overall antiemetics used in the operating room and a 22% decrease in antiemetics given in the PACU. The primary limitation of this study was due to the nature of a retrospective study; researchers were unable to determine if Post-ease was given after antiemetics were used or if the aromatherapy was administered as an intervention before antiemetic administration.

A comparison of blend essential oils was not researched within the time frame selected for this systematic review, nor were studies comparing blends referenced in each respective study

referred to. However, blend comparisons could deduce which “ideal scent” hospitals should begin introducing into the post-operative setting if there are barriers to hospitals choosing multiple scents. The essential oils used in Post-Ease use lemon, whereas QueaseEASE uses ginger. Both blends utilize the same base scents of peppermint, lavender, and ginger, signifying that those core scents are effective for the specific problem of PONV. This study could also indicate that spearmint and ginger don’t significantly change the blend’s efficacy. It is important to mention that in regard to standalone scents researched, no study from 2019 to 2023 researched spearmint aromatherapy for PONV. One study conducted in Iran examined the efficacy of lemon essential oil on lower extremity fracture repairs with a sample size of 90 patients (Rambod et al., 2023). Essential oils were dropped onto a face mask preoperatively, onto the patient’s gown intraoperatively, and onto a cotton ball that was placed into the patient’s oxygen mask postoperatively. The control used was bitter almond oil, which does not contain a scent. This study found that lemon aromatherapy resulted in 0% of the experimental group vomiting, versus 24.4% of the control group. Additionally, 0% of the intervention group experienced nausea lasting longer than 1 hour, versus 31.1% of the control group. 0% of the experimental group received antiemetic medications, compared to 8.9% of the control group that did receive antiemetics. Since the surgery examined in this study was of the lower extremities, there is a possibility overall PONV rates were lower compared to cholecystectomies, laparoscopic, or gynecological surgeries (Nagarekha et al., 2016). While no research has been conducted on a direct comparison between lemon and spearmint, the efficacy of Rambod et al.’s (2023) study could infer that lemon essential oil in a PONV blend is more effective.

Ginger Aromatherapy

Ginger essential oil aromatherapy was also researched as a standalone scent. In a study on patients undergoing same-day short-stay surgeries, the control group used fewer anti-nausea

medications than the placebo group (Farrington et al., 2019). To reiterate, this study did not split up the results of all aromatherapy scents utilized and solely referenced them as “experimental group results.” Another study examined the effects of ginger aromatherapy on a similar type of procedure, ambulatory surgery (Hunt et al., 2013). 67.1% of participants in the ginger group reported lower levels of PON. The placebo group had the lowest number of participants reporting a decrease in PON (39.7%), and the isopropyl alcohol group experienced mildly effective results, with 51.3% of participants having a reduction in PON. Thus, adjudging ginger essential oil to be effective in reducing PONV. However, ginger did not yield as large of a decrease in PONV as peppermint essential oil (Farrington et al., 2019), so it would not be the ideal essential oil to introduce to hospitals beginning to incorporate aromatherapy into their post-operative patient care. Another study examining the efficacy of ginger aromatherapy for elective surgeries, including gynecological, gastrointestinal, orthopedic, head & neck, and urology, used ginger essential oil versus a placebo of pure water saturated on a gauze pad (Karaman et al., 2019). PON scores from before the aromatherapy intervention to after improved in 43.5% of the placebo group versus 65.2% of the ginger group, meaning ginger effectively lowers PON. The group that received the highest rates of improvement was the lavender essential oil group, as 82.6% of participants reported that their PON decreased. The rose aromatherapy and placebo group had the highest rates of vomiting among the participants. The rose group also had similar PON improvement rates to the placebo group, deducing that rose essential oil is not as effective in aromatherapy as lavender or ginger. Amongst all experimental groups, after receiving aromatherapy, 46.2% of patients experienced vomiting, and 50% of patients needed antiemetic medication, meaning aromatherapy is by no means a complete replacement for antiemetic medication. Overall, ginger aromatherapy was more effective than the placebo but not as effective as other scents it was compared to. Blend aromatherapy and lavender

aromatherapy lowered PONV at higher rates than ginger essential oils (Fearington et al., 2019; Hunt et al., 2013; Karaman et al., 2019).

Cardamom Aromatherapy

Cardamom essential oil aromatherapy's effectiveness in reducing PONV in women with spinal anesthesia undergoing elective cesarean section was also studied (Khatiban et al., 2022). This study contained a sample size of 70 participants and measured the amount of antiemetics used, PON, and retching. Nausea decreased by 47.2% in the experimental group, compared to 26.8% in the normal saline placebo group. The experimental group experienced significantly lower rates of nausea after the intervention was implemented. Retching was experienced by 20.0% of participants in the experimental group, compared to 45.7% of the placebo group. Thus, it can be concluded that cardamom aromatherapy in this sample size was effective in decreasing rates of postoperative nausea. Additionally, the amount of antiemetics used was lower in the experimental group compared to the placebo group. The primary limitation to this study is that the scent used has a cultural significance in Iran, which could possibly affect how successful cardamom aromatherapy is on patients from other countries. Likewise if scents used in outside countries were brought to Iran.

Efficacy

Aromatherapy uses essential oils in either an inhaler form, a cotton ball soaked with essential oil waved in from of the patient's nose, or a cotton round soaked with essential oil attached to a patient's gown given once a patient experienced PONV after surgery (Fearington et al., 2019; Hodge et al., 2014; Karsten et al., 2020; Marsh et al., 2021). Aromatherapy scents have varying rates of efficacy. Blends of various aromatherapy have been found to have a higher degree of effectiveness compared to single scents (Hodge et al., 2014). The method of delivery of aromatherapy did not yield any significance to the results.

The typical scents seen were peppermint, ginger, lavender, cardamom, lemon, rose, or a combination of scents. These scents were compared to the placebo of no scent and were found to have around the same efficacy rate in reducing PONV, except for rose, which increased the rate of vomiting among participants (Karaman et al., 2019). For peppermint, ginger, and lavender essential oils, participants experienced lower levels of nausea within 15 minutes to an hour, giving those three essential oils statistically significant results (Karaman et al., 2019; Karsten et al., 2020; Marsh et al., 2021). In a randomized study, the patients' comments revealed that aromatherapy was more effective for patients experiencing lower nausea levels postoperatively (Hodge et al., 2014). A 2014 study compared the effects of a normal saline placebo, ginger essential oil, blend essential oil, and isopropyl alcohol (Hodge et al.). A higher percentage of those who used a blend of essential oils (82.4%) reported relief of PONV compared to ginger (67.1%). This statistic is compared to the higher percentage of participants who asked for antiemetics after receiving the placebo (80.8%) and isopropyl alcohol (71.8%) (Hunt et al., 2013). The efficacy of the scents lavender, peppermint, and ginger is evident compared to normal saline or water placebo. Effectiveness was also determined by the amount of antiemetic medications requested by the patients, which plays a role in the cost efficiency of aromatherapy. The placebo of no scent or normal saline had the highest number of participants taking antiemetics (Fearrington et al., 2019). The method by which aromatherapy was delivered did not yield significant results (Hodge et al., 2014; Hunt et al., 2013; Trandel-Korenchuk et al., 2022).

Strengths

The strengths of all studies included a focus on the most effective types of essential oils. The studies included a placebo of saline and experimental essential oils of peppermint, lavender, ginger, spearmint, or blends of multiple oils. The use of similar essential oils made the comparison between studies more corroborative. Two studies included the percentage of

essential oils used, which contributed to the conclusion that the concentration percent does have a slight difference in efficacy but does not yield a significant difference in antiemetic effects (Ahmadi et al., 2020; Maghami et al., 2020). For example, when comparing 10% peppermint essential oil to 30% peppermint essential oil, the 30% reduced nausea by 8.7% more than the 10% essential oil (Ahmadi et al., 2020). However, both the 30% and 10% essential oils reduced nausea at a significant rate, thus leading to the conclusion that strength is not a major factor in the rate of nausea reduction (Ahmadi et al., 2020). The studies all assessed levels of nausea and vomiting at different intervals after the intervention to synthesize results of which essential oils worked quicker. The greatest strength throughout all studies was the comparison between aromatherapy results and amount of antiemetic use (Abril et al., 2019; Ahmadi et al., 2020; Anderson & Gross, 2004; Fearington et al., 2019; Hodge et al., 2014; Hunt et al., 2013; Karaman et al., 2019; Khatiban et al., 2022; Maghami et al., 2020; Marsh et al., 2021; Norton et al., 2022; Rambod et al., 2023; Trandel-Korechuk et al., 2022). This comparison can help determine and conclude the effectiveness of aromatherapy (Hines et al., 2018).

The studies were also reproducible, as they specified the mode of administration, duration of administration, and scents used. Only one study did not disclose exactly which scent was used, aside from being a blend (Trandel-Korechuk et al., 2022). The studies examined were also randomized, as high-risk populations were scattered across groups. One study ended up having more patients with a history of PONV in the experimental group. Still, patients in the intervention groups used less antiemetics than the control group despite a greater PONV history (Fearington et al., 2019). Most studies used a placebo of either normal saline, water, or bitter almond oil to compare the results of aromatherapy with (Ahmadi et al., 2020; Anderson & Gross, 2004; Fearington et al., 2019; Hodge et al., 2014; Hunt et al., 2013; Karaman et al., 2019; Khatiban et al., 2022; Maghami et al., 2020; Marsh et al., 2021; Rambod et al., 2023). Each

study used a clearly defined nausea scale to determine the efficacy of scents (Abril et al., 2019; Ahmadi et al., 2020; Anderson & Gross, 2004; Fearrington et al., 2019; Hodge et al., 2014; Hunt et al., 2013; Karaman et al., 2019; Khatiban et al., 2022; Maghami et al., 2020; Marsh et al., 2021; Norton et al., 2022; Rambod et al., 2023; Trandel-Korenychuk et al., 2022). Many studies have compared aromatherapy administration to antiemetic usage to determine whether antiemetic use has decreased (Abril et al., 2019; Ahmadi et al., 2020; Anderson & Gross, 2004; Fearrington et al., 2019; Hunt et al., 2013; Khatiban et al., 2022; Maghami et al., 2020; Marsh et al., 2021; Norton et al., 2022; Rambod et al., 2023; Trandel-Korenychuk et al., 2022).

Limitations

The primary limitation found across all studies was the sample size being small (Abril et al., 2019; Anderson & Gross, 2004; Hodge et al., 2014; Hunt et al., 2013; Karaman et al., 2019; Maghami et al., 2020; Norton et al., 2022). Prospective participants were chosen before surgery, and their participation in the study depended on whether they experienced PONV. Therefore, the final sample sizes dwindled, and effectiveness or lack thereof may have been based on patient subjectivity. The small sample sizes restricted some results to be considered significant (Anderson & Gross, 2004). A secondary limitation found across studies was the difficulty of concealing the placebo versus the experimental (Anderson & Gross, 2004; Khatiban et al., 2022). Staff and patients were well aware of which category they were placed in due to the strong scent of aromatherapy. Not all essential oil concentrations were revealed, as potency could have an effect on efficacy (Trandel-Korenychuk et al., 2022).

The heterogeneity of all studies made cross-compariison difficult to accomplish. When comparing articles, surgery types were not similar throughout all articles, meaning some participants may have received higher doses of anesthetics or more invasive surgeries, which could affect their level of PONV. Studies dating a decade back have shown levels of

effectiveness in aromatherapy, yet aromatherapy is not a standardized practice throughout all hospitals in the United States. Hence, adjunct research needs to be conducted on why aromatherapy is not a standardized practice implemented across hospitals when research supports it as a non-invasive, cost-effective treatment method.

Clinical Indications

Aromatherapy yields positive results in lowering PONV. Clinically, this research is vital in finding non-pharmacological treatment options with no significant side effects to enhance the experience of a patient's recovery process. In the clinical setting, it is vital to select the scents that are deemed effective (peppermint, spearmint, ginger, lavender). Blends appeared to be more effective than sole essential oil aromatherapies being administered (Hunt et al., 2013; Marsh et al., 2021; Norton et al., 2022; Trandel-Korenychuk et al., 2022). It is vital to note that no study suggested aromatherapy as a replacement for antiemetic medication. Aromatherapy is a treatment recommended to be used in conjunction with antiemetics to potentially decrease the use of anti-nausea medication.

Culture may also play a role in the significance of aromatherapy used. Four studies were conducted in Iran, with the following scents used: cardamom, 30% peppermint, 10% peppermint, and lemon (Ahmadi et al., 2020; Khatiban et al., 2022; Maghami et al., 2020; Rambod et al., 2023). Cardamom and lemon, with the exception of an aromatherapy blend with lemon, were the only independent scents used strictly in Iran (Khatiban et al., 2022; Rambod et al., 2023). This is compared to studies examined from the United States, which primarily used only peppermint essentials or blends of peppermint, ginger, and lavender. This leads to the inference of cultural significance surrounding certain scents, which may not be translated to different regions of the world.

Aromatherapy is an affordable and non-invasive treatment option that addresses the issue in the current practice of administering excess medications postoperatively and mitigates the risk of adverse effects from antiemetics. To implement the intervention of aromatherapy, essential oil sticks or the selected method of aromatherapy per facility would need to be supplied. Multiple scents are preferred to surpass the barriers of allergies and patients' personal preferences. Next, nurses working in the post-anesthesia care units (PACU) will need to be educated on how to use the aromatherapy sticks and how to document use in the electronic medical record (EMR) (Trandel-Korenychuk et al., 2022). Aromatherapy inhalers were established to be cost-efficient, with a net cost of \$0.50 per inhaler, which could possibly be even cheaper (Fearington et al., 2019). This is compared to antiemetics medications, which can which can cost patients an additional estimated \$75 (Trandel-Korenychuk et al., 2022). At a study site where Post-Ease aromatherapy was initiated, materials and labor costs totaled two times lower than oral antiemetics and three times lower than intravenous antiemetic medications (Marsh et al., 2021). This is due to a decreased amount of antiemetics utilized while the study was being conducted. Aromatherapy sticks do have a higher price point compared to alcohol swabs typically used in the place of aromatherapy; costs were saved due to not needing to contact the anesthesiologist to monitor the patient and from timely patient discharges (Trandel-Korenychuk et al., 2022). Thus, aromatherapy is a practical, evidence-based, non-pharmacological treatment for patients with PONV.

Conclusion

Select types of essential oils (peppermint, ginger, lavender, and blends) have exhibited statistically significant results in reducing the amount of PONV (Abril et al., 2019; Ahmadi et al., 2020; Anderson & Gross, 2004; Fearington et al., 2019; Hodge et al., 2014; Hunt et al., 2013; Karaman et al., 2019; Maghami et al., 2020; Marsh et al., 2021; Norton et al., 2022;

Trandel-Korenchuk et al., 2022). Non-pharmacological relief methods after surgery should be encouraged to help decrease the number of additional medications given to the patient, reduce the excess side effects experienced by the patient from taking antiemetics, and provide a better hospital experience overall. These studies give a reference to aromatherapy efficacy in regards to type of surgery, age, and gender.

To expand the scents offered in hospitals and to combat the potential barriers of allergens or insensitivities, further research on different essential oils will need to be completed. Blend aromatherapy is effective for use across various types of surgeries and in pediatric and adult patients. Thus, it is also crucial to research how aromatherapy can be implemented as a standard practice across hospitals in the United States, such as barriers to institutions implementing aromatherapy in their current state, given the financial and patient benefits it could yield to medical centers.

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Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
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Table 1

Table of Evidence: Effects of Aromatherapy on PONV

(Abril et al., 2019)	Assess the effectiveness of peppermint aromatherapy on postoperative nausea and vomiting in female patients who have undergone laparoscopic abdominal surgery.	<p><u>Design:</u> Observational</p> <p><u>Setting:</u> PACU in a non-academic hospital (New York, U.S.)</p> <p><u>IV:</u> peppermint essential oil</p> <p><u>Control group:</u> N/A</p> <p><u>DV:</u> amount of antiemetics used, PONV</p> <p><u>Method of delivering aromatherapy:</u> Sniffer</p> <p><u>Measurement:</u> 4-point Visual Analogue Scale to report nausea before and after PACU admittance</p> <p><u>Sampling:</u> Convenience sample; Adults female patients undergoing laparoscopic abdominal surgery</p>	<p><u>Sample:</u> N=35 women undergoing laparoscopic abdominal surgery; mean age: 42.5</p> <p><u>Key Findings:</u> Out of the sample of 35 patients, 15 patients reported nausea. 73% of these patients reported a complete resolution of nausea by the time they were discharged by the PACU. 88% of patients who did not receive any antiemetic medications reported resolution of their nausea solely through aromatherapy. Those who used aromatherapy Sniffers in the PACU were 3x more likely to use a Sniffer post-PACU. However, due to the small sample size, no direct causal</p>	<p><u>Conclusions:</u> Peppermint aromatherapy is effective in decreasing PONV in adult women who have undergone abdominal laparoscopic surgery</p> <p><u>Limitations:</u> The small sample size caused the results yielded to not be statistically significant due to the sample size being too small. The limited number clinical nurse investigators available to enroll participants resulted in a small sample size. There was also no placebo sniffer used, meaning the results could be accurately skewed to favor aromatherapy versus the only other comparison of no sniffer used.</p>	IV (Polit & Beck, 2018)	Yes, since each patient's history with PONV was taken into account, along with whether aromatherapy usage deterred antiemetics from being prescribed. However, since no results were found to be statistically significant, creating a larger sample size in the future would benefit the study.
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Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
		<p><u>Anesthesia used:</u> general anesthesia</p> <p><u>Inclusion:</u> ≥18 years of age, female, post-operative from same-day or 23-hour laparoscopic abdominal surgery</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> pregnant, breastfeeding, allergies or intolerance to peppermint essential oil</p>	relationship between peppermint aromatherapy and PONV could be established.	<p><u>Notes:</u> Surgeries included: cholecystectomy, hysterectomy with salpingoophorectomy, only salpingoophorectomy, tubal ligation, sleeve gastrectomy, ovarian cystectomy, myomectomy, revision of fundoplication wedge resection, resection of abdominal mass, umbilical hernia repair</p>		
(Ahmadi et al., 2020)	Determine the effectiveness of 30% peppermint oil versus 10% peppermint oil in reducing PONV in patients who received abdominal surgery.	<p><u>Design:</u> Single-blind randomized controlled</p> <p><u>Setting:</u> Surgical ward (Kermanshah, Iran)</p> <p><u>IV:</u> 30% peppermint oil, 10% peppermint oil</p> <p><u>Control group:</u> placebo (2 mL of distilled water with green food coloring)</p> <p><u>DV:</u> Amount of antiemetics used, PONV</p>	<p><u>Sample:</u> N = 120, N = 40 allocated to each group (10%, 30%, placebo)</p> <p><u>Key Findings:</u> Both the 10% and 30% peppermint were successful in reducing PONV, compared to the placebo, which did not have a statistically significant decrease in PONV. The 10% peppermint oil group experienced an 11.8%</p>	<p><u>Conclusions:</u> Aromatherapy is effective in decreasing PONV, which aligns with studies already done on the topic. Essential oil potency does not have a significant effect on nausea levels, as both the 10% and the 30% group had similar decreases in nausea.</p> <p><u>Limitations:</u> The study included various types of abdominal surgeries, which could have</p>	Level II (Polit & Beck, 2018)	Yes, this study is evidence based practice. The specification of the scent and percentage used is useful in determining how to create aromatherapy sticks to be distributed to different hospitals and

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
		<p><u>Method of delivering aromatherapy:</u> essential oils placed on gauze, then patients smelled the gauze</p> <p><u>Measurement:</u> Nausea visual analog scale (NVAS)</p> <p><u>Sampling:</u> convenience sample, then randomly assigned essential oil percentage or placebo</p> <p><u>Anesthesia used:</u> General anesthesia</p> <p><u>Inclusion:</u> patients admitted to the surgical ward for abdominal surgery (ileus, cancer, gallbladder disease), general anesthesia used, NVAS ≥ 20, ages 15-65 years, alert, no respiratory disease, limited or no antiemetic use</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> allergies to essential oils, excess antiemetic or narcotic use, symptoms of allergies (SOB, coughing)</p>	<p>decrease in nausea from before the intervention to after. The 30% peppermint oil group experienced a 20.5% decrease in nausea after the intervention. The control group experienced a decrease in nausea by 3.2%.</p>	<p>had an impact on the severity and length of nausea felt. The space between the control group and intervention group beds were more than two meters, but the smell could have spread, skewing the results.</p>		<p>decrease costs. The large sample size makes the results significant.</p>

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
(Anderson & Gross, 2004)	Compare the effects of peppermint essential oils, isopropyl alcohol, or placebo (normal saline) on postoperative nausea and vomiting.	<p><u>Design:</u> randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study</p> <p><u>Setting:</u> Post-anesthesia care unit of an ambulatory surgery center</p> <p><u>IV:</u> Peppermint essential oils, 70% isopropyl alcohol, and placebo (normal saline) on a saturated gauze pad</p> <p><u>DV:</u> Level of PONV</p> <p><u>Measurement:</u> 100-mm visual analogue scale rating nausea level (0 mm = extremely dissatisfied; 100 mm = fully satisfied), and incidence of vomiting</p> <p><u>Sampling:</u> Random sample</p> <p><u>Inclusion:</u> ≥18 years old, ambulatory surgery on study day, able to provide informed consent, incidence of nausea post-operatively</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> No nausea or</p>	<p><u>Sample:</u> N=32 ambulatory surgery patients</p> <p><u>Key Findings:</u> Effects of aromatherapy were not affected by type of surgery, age, gender, or if they received general anesthesia. 18% of patients in the alcohol group, 20% of the peppermint group, and 8% of the saline group, requested emergency antiemetics after the two-minute mark of receiving aromatherapy. Overall patient satisfaction with nausea management graded on a visual analog scale was 90.3% for the alcohol group, 86.3% for the peppermint group, and 83.7% for the saline group.</p>	<p><u>Conclusions:</u> Aromatherapy of all groups, including the placebo, effectively reduced nausea levels in participants. However, there was no significant difference amongst experimental groups and the placebo group in terms of how much PONV decreased. The study hypothesized that the breathing pattern was the reason that PONV decreased in all groups.</p> <p><u>Limitations:</u> The IRB required informed consent be given to all participants, decreasing the “blindness” of the study. Additionally, post-operative nausea decreases with time, so the inevitable decrease may have coincided with the administration of aromatherapy. The sample size of the study was also limited.</p>	II (Polit & Beck, 2018)	Yes, it serves as an important comparison piece to other studies replicated in the future. Studies completed further on have vastly different results, possibly due to the change in anesthetics used, or due to the change of essential oils and aromatherapy agents used. The results showed lower efficacy of aromatherapy compared to the placebo compared to studies discussed in

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
		vomiting, did not require anesthesia				the article, thus the study is valuable to examine why effectiveness was lower.
(Fearington et al., 2019)	Investigate whether aromatherapy using essential oils in adults decreases the incidence of PONV and reduces the need of antiemetic medications.	<p><u>Design:</u> Double blind cross-sectional study</p> <p><u>Setting:</u> Urban educational hospital – surgical center</p> <p><u>IV:</u> peppermint, ginger, or combo of both essential oils</p> <p><u>DV:</u> amount of antiemetics used, PONV</p> <p><u>Measurement:</u> Nausea was tested for using a verbal descriptive scale</p> <p><u>Sampling:</u> Convenience sample; Adults patients undergoing same day surgical procedures or short stay surgical procedures</p> <p><u>Inclusion:</u> ≥18 years of age, follow directions,</p>	<p><u>Sample:</u> N=322 patients admitted for same-day surgery; Control group (N=179); Intervention group (N=143)</p> <p><u>Key Findings:</u> The control group used more antiemetics (0.53 ± 0.85) compared to the experimental group (0.15 ± 0.47) ($P < .001$). Differences in the type of inhaler used (ginger, peppermint, combination) was not statistically significant ($P = 0.62$). The experimental group had more participants with a history of PONV (14% of participants compared to 4.5% of</p>	<p><u>Conclusions:</u> Patients in the intervention groups used less antiemetics than the control group, despite greater PONV history. Ginger, peppermint, and combo essential oils yielded similar results.</p> <p><u>Limitations:</u> No placebo was used, aromatherapy results were only compared using a retrospective chart review. Convenience sampling was also used, which lessens the strength of the data.</p>	II (Polit & Beck, 2018)	Yes, however the limitations of convenience sampling makes the findings not as credible as random sampling. Also, the type of anesthesia used on the patients was not discussed, but could have affected how severe the PONV was. Aromatherapy was used both pre-operatively and post-operatively

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
		<p>read/comprehend/write English, ability to give informed consent</p> <p><i>Exclusion:</i> PMH of respiratory disorder that could be triggered by aromatherapy, allergy or sensitivity to peppermint or ginger</p>	<p>participants in the control group).</p>			<p>y, which makes it difficult to compare to studies where aromatherapy was only used post-op.</p>
(Hodge et al., 2014)	<p>Compare efficacy of aromatherapy as treatments for postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) in children and adults compared to a placebo unscented inhalant.</p>	<p><i>Design:</i> Prospective randomized double blind study.</p> <p><i>Setting:</i> Pacific Northwest; One 250-bed military medical center</p> <p><i>IV:</i> Aromatic inhaler (QueaseEase – lavender, peppermint, ginger, and spearmint oils) or unscented inhaler</p> <p><i>DV:</i> Level of PONV</p> <p><i>Measurement:</i> 10 point Likert scale; interview with 10% of participants; questionnaires asking about satisfaction of treatment and effectivity of aromatherapy</p>	<p><i>Sample:</i> N= 121 patients with postoperative nausea (PON)</p> <p><i>Key Findings:</i> Decrease in PONV in both aromatherapy and placebo group (P < .01).</p> <p>Patient’s perceived aromatherapy effectiveness was 3 points higher in the aromatherapy group compared to the placebo group. Out of a 6-point scale, the treatment group dropped nausea from an initial nausea score of 5.4 to a follow up score of 3.4,</p>	<p>Aromatherapy and the placebo treatment had similar results in terms of lessening the amount of post-operative nausea and vomiting. While the aromatherapy inhaler proved to decrease nausea more than the placebo, there was not significant enough evidence to prove the aromatherapy as a viable treatment versus antiemetic medications.</p> <p><i>Limitations:</i> Not all selected participants experienced PONV, so the sample size decreased. In some cases where patients did experience PONV, the</p>	<p>II (Polit & Beck, 2018)</p>	<p>Yes, but we should conduct further research with a larger sample size and specified scents. Statistical findings between placebo and experimental group were similar although patient comments expressed perceived effectiveness</p>

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
		<p><u>Sampling:</u> Convenience sample</p> <p><u>Inclusion:</u> surgical adult patients projected to be admitted post-op anesthesia, nausea on the postoperative inpatient unit, able to provide informed consent, intact sense of smell, ability to rank effectiveness on Likert scale</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> patients with allergies to the following: peppermint, lavender, spearmint</p>	<p>compared to the placebo group, which had a decrease of nausea from an initial score of 5.6 to a follow up score of 4.4.</p> <p>Satisfaction of nausea treatment was similar – both groups rated satisfaction 6.8-7.1 on Likert scale.</p>	<p>inhaler was not used as the nurse already administered an IV anti-emetic or the nurse did not have enough time to instruct the patient to use the inhaler. The study took patient comments from 10 participants, in which one participant stated the aromatherapy made their nausea worse. Therefore, personal scent preference is a larger barrier. There was no evidence collected on the efficacy of anti-nausea medications used when aromatherapy rendered ineffective, making comparison impossible to do.</p>		<p>of experiment group.</p>
(Hunt et al., 2013)	<p>Compare the effects of ginger essential oils, essential oil blend, and isopropyl alcohol on postoperative</p>	<p><u>Design:</u> Prospective four-arm placebo controlled clinical trial.</p> <p><u>Setting:</u> Ambulatory surgical site (Charlotte, North Carolina)</p> <p><u>IV:</u> Ginger essential oils, essential oil blend (ginger, spearmint, peppermint, and</p>	<p><u>Sample:</u> N=300 patients; randomized in 4 aromatherapy groups, each with 75 patients</p> <p><u>Key Findings:</u> The blend aromatherapy and ginger aromatherapy were most effective in reducing</p>	<p><u>Limitations:</u> Two participants complained the aromatherapy had an unpleasant smell, which was hypothesized to be ingredient degradation of the essential oils, excluding those participants from the</p>	<p>II (Polit & Beck, 2018)</p>	<p>Yes, the sample size was large and diverse. The study made it evident that a placebo of saline is appropriate,</p>

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
	nausea and vomiting.	<p>cardamom), 70% isopropyl alcohol, placebo [normal saline (NS)] placed on a saturated gauze pad</p> <p><i>DV:</i> Level of PONV</p> <p><i>Measurement:</i> descriptive 4-point Likert scale (0 = no nausea, 1 = mild, 2 = moderate, 3 = severe)</p> <p><i>Sampling:</i> Random sample; grouped via Wilcoxon ranked-sum test</p> <p><i>Inclusion:</i> ≥18 years old, able to provide informed consent, surgery planned for the day of study, nausea in the post-operative unit</p> <p><i>Exclusion:</i> Concurrent use of antiplatelets or anticoagulants, bleeding disorders, allergies to ginger, spearmint, peppermint, or cardamom</p>	<p>PONV. 71.8% of patients in the alcohol group and 80.8% of patients in the NS group received emergency antiemetics; compared to 55.5% of the participants in the ginger group and 40.5% of patients in the blend group that received antiemetics after aromatherapy. 67.1% of participants in the ginger group and 82.4% of participants in the blend group reported reduced levels of PON. This is compared to 39.7% of participants in the NS group and 51.3% of participants in the alcohol group that reported reduced PON.</p>	<p>study. This denotes that not all essential oil blends will be chemically stable for patient use. Additionally, the exclusion of patients with history of leading disorders due to ginger being a natural anticoagulant poses a disadvantage as not all patients can be included. The aromatherapy effects were only tested at a 5-minute interval, and longer effects were not examined. The sample size was also too small to investigate how aromatherapy affects patients with various risk factors. The small sample size also made it more difficult to determine a significant difference in POV between the control and experimental group.</p>		<p>and determined the effectiveness of various essential oils to reduce nausea. When applying this literature into real life scenarios, using isopropyl alcohol may be more convenient due to the ease of accessing alcohol pads, compared to essential oils.</p>
(Karaman et al., 2019)	Investigate if patients	<i>Design:</i> randomized 4-armed control study	<i>Sample:</i> N=184 patients; randomized in 4	Rose essential oil had similar results on nausea	II (Polit & Beck,	Yes, however a larger sample

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
	<p>smelling various essential oils before surgery will reduce postoperative anxiety and pain.</p>	<p><i>Setting:</i> Gaziosmanpasa University, School of Medicine; Turkey</p> <p><i>IV:</i> Aromatic inhaler (gauze with two drops of ginger, lavender or rose essential oil) or unscented inhaler (two drops of pure water)</p> <p><i>DV:</i> Level of PONV</p> <p><i>Measurement:</i> 0-3 post-op nausea Likert scale, 0-3 post-op vomiting Likert scale, need of antiemetic medication</p> <p><i>Sampling:</i> Simple random</p> <p><i>Inclusion:</i> patient experiencing PONV after undergoing anesthesia; time frame: April 2016 to November 2018</p> <p><i>Exclusion:</i> <17 years of age or >65 years of age; using antiemetic medication, past cardiovascular/psychological/pulmonary disease history, allergies to rose, lavender, ginger, poor</p>	<p>aromatherapy groups: lavender, rose, or ginger essential oil, or pure water placebo.</p> <p><i>Key Findings:</i> Initial nausea scores were similar amongst all groups. PON scores from before the aromatherapy intervention to after improved in 43.5% of the placebo group, 82.6% of the lavender group, 47.8% of the rose group, and 65.2% of the ginger group. After patients received aromatherapy, 46.2% of patients experienced vomiting, and 50% of patients needed antiemetic medication. Rose aromatherapy and placebo had the highest percentage of participants vomit (87% and 60.9% respectively).</p>	<p>and vomiting as placebo. Lavender and ginger essential oils did have a positive effect on reducing the incidence of post-op nausea and vomiting.</p> <p><i>Limitations:</i> Chemical components of each essential oil were not researched, as potency and composition could have affected results. Not all selected participants experienced PONV, so the sample size was smaller than anticipated.</p>	2018)	<p>size is required. The vast difference between lavender and ginger essential oils compared to rose and the placebo showed that essential oils can be a low risk treatment option for PONV.</p>

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
(Khatiban et al., 2022)	Determine the effectiveness of cardamom essential oil aromatherapy in women with spinal anesthesia undergoing elective cesarean section in decreasing postoperative nausea (PON), retching, and antiemetic use.	<p>sense of smell</p> <p><u>Design:</u> single-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled study</p> <p><u>Setting:</u> University hospital (Iran)</p> <p><u>IV:</u> cardamom essential oil</p> <p><u>Control group:</u> normal saline (NS)</p> <p><u>DV:</u> Amount of antiemetics used, PON and retching</p> <p><u>Method of delivering aromatherapy:</u> plastic bag with gauze soaked in NS with or without cardamom essential oil</p> <p><u>Measurement:</u> visual analog scale (VAS) from 0-100</p> <p><u>Sampling:</u> convenience sample</p> <p><u>Anesthesia used:</u> Spinal anesthesia</p>	<p><u>Sample:</u> N = 70; N = 35 allocated to placebo and experimental group</p> <p><u>Key Findings:</u> The average duration of childbirth of the cesarean section for the placebo group was 33 minutes, and 29.97 minutes for the experimental group, meaning there was not a statistically significant difference between both groups. Out of a 100-point scale, nausea severity decreased by 26.75 points in the placebo group, and 47.15 points in the cardamom group. After 5 minutes of the intervention, 62.9% of the experimental group did not have nausea, versus 34.3% of the placebo group. Also</p>	<p><u>Conclusions:</u> Aromatherapy is effective in decreasing PON, which aligns with studies already done on the topic. The amount of antiemetics used in the experimental group was lower than the placebo group. The amount of nausea after five minutes of aromatherapy was also lower in the experimental group versus the placebo group. The instance of vomiting was similar amongst both groups. However, there were no statistically significant results between both groups. The severity of nausea decreased over time in both groups.</p> <p><u>Limitations:</u> Short term use of cardamom essential oil and the recognition of cardamom essential oil as</p>	Level II (Polit & Beck, 2018)	Yes, this is EBP. The study determined how cardamom is a member of the ginger family, and other studies have shown the effectiveness of ginger to reduce PONV. However, the results were not statistically significant throughout the study, meaning cardamom may not be as effective of an essential oil for PONV.

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
		<p><i>Inclusion:</i> women undergoing elective cesarean section under spinal anesthesia, singleton delivery, no antiemetics used within 24 hours before surgery</p> <p><i>Exclusion:</i> history of nausea in third trimester, respiratory distress, allergies to essential oils, motion sickness, drug or alcohol or smoking abuse history, general anesthesia, repeat (2+) spinal anesthesia attempts, complicated c-section delivery</p>	<p>after 5 minutes of the intervention, 80.0% of the experimental group did not experience retching, versus 54.3% of the placebo group.</p>	<p>experimental by the participants. Scent used may have a cultural difference regarding efficacy.</p>		
(Maghami et al., 2020)	<p>Determine the effectiveness of peppermint essential oil aromatherapy to decrease PONV after open-heart cardiac surgery.</p>	<p><i>Design:</i> single-blind randomized clinical trial</p> <p><i>Setting:</i> Educational hospital (Kashan, Iran)</p> <p><i>IV:</i> 10% peppermint essential oil</p> <p><i>Control group:</i> nebulizer without essential oil (only 10 ml distilled water)</p> <p><i>DV:</i> Amount of antiemetics used, PONV</p>	<p><i>Sample:</i> N = 60, N = 30 received intervention and N = 26 received the placebo; majority of surgeries were coronary artery bypass grafts (N = 22)</p> <p><i>Key Findings:</i> The average severity of nausea was 2.12 times higher in the control group compared to the intervention group. The</p>	<p><i>Conclusions:</i> 10% peppermint aromatherapy is effective in decreasing PONV in adults who have undergone open-heart surgery. Suggested adjunct treatment for PONV in the future (alongside antiemetics).</p> <p><i>Limitations:</i> Results may be limited d/t study being conducted in a hospital, thus results may</p>	<p>Level II (Polit & Beck, 2018)</p>	<p>Yes, this study showed statistically significant results in a specific patient population. PONV was reduced in the experimental group, meaning the intervention is an acceptable</p>

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
		<p><u>Method of delivering aromatherapy:</u> nebulizer aromatherapy</p> <p><u>Measurement:</u> nausea and vomiting assessing scale (4 questions about the severity, frequency, and duration of nausea and the frequency of vomiting episodes)</p> <p><u>Sampling:</u> Convenience sample</p> <p><u>Anesthesia used:</u> Not specified</p> <p><u>Inclusion:</u> Elective surgery, ≥ 18 years old, ability to answer questions in Persian, full post-operative consciousness</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> allergies to essential oils, history of respiratory disease, endotracheal (ET) tube >24 hours, reintubation within 1 hour of ET tube removal, return to operating room, death of patient</p>	<p>overall average duration of nausea was 2.32 times higher in the control group compared to the intervention group. Highest incidence of PONV was within 4 hours of extubation. Statistically significant decrease in duration, severity, and frequency of nausea within the first 4 hours of extubation. Statistically significant decrease in frequency of vomiting within the first 4 hours of extubation.</p>	<p>not be able to be generalized to the public.</p>		<p>adjunct therapy to antiemetics.</p>

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
(Marsh et al., 2021)	Evaluate the effectiveness of an essential oil blend to reduce PONV and antiemetic administration in orthopedic postoperative patients.	<p><u>Design:</u> retrospective cohort study</p> <p><u>Setting:</u> orthopedic post-operative units of not-for-profit regional medical center (New Hampshire, U.S.)</p> <p><u>IV:</u> Post-Ease (blend of lavender, peppermint, ginger, and lemon essential oils)</p> <p><u>Control group:</u> no aromatherapy</p> <p><u>DV:</u> amount of antiemetics used, PONV, incidence of retching or queasiness</p> <p><u>Method of delivering aromatherapy:</u> cotton round with drops of essential oil attached to patient's gown with a sticker adhesive postoperatively</p> <p><u>Measurement:</u> amount of antiemetics administered by reflecting back on electronic medication administration records of patients</p>	<p><u>Sample:</u> N=810 post total knee/hip replacement surgeries in 2019 and N=886 total knee/hip replacement surgeries in 2020; average age of patients: 67.</p> <p><u>Key Findings:</u> Statistically significant decrease in incidence of antiemetic administration (21%; $p \leq .05$) when aromatherapy was given. The overall amount of antiemetics given amongst cases was reduced by 21% during surgery cases. A 22% decrease of antiemetics given in the PACU also resulted.</p>	<p><u>Conclusions:</u> Aromatherapy is effective in decreasing PONV and thus antiemetic use in the orthopedic population who are post-PACU and close to discharge.</p> <p><u>Limitations:</u> Geographic location was limited to central New Hampshire. Since the sample population was random, the patient's history of PONV, type of anesthesia used, or comorbidities were not factored into the study. Since the study was a reflection on the MAR of patients, the limited documentation caused a barrier in determining who received Post-Ease as a treatment and which patient did not need any antiemetic intervention. Therefore, the study was unable to determine whether Post-Ease was only given to</p>	IV (Polit & Beck, 2018)	No. This study failed to take into account anesthesia types used, opioids used, patient history, and whether the Post-Ease actually eliminated the need for antiemetic in patients who were documented to have PONV.

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
		<p><u>Sampling:</u> Convenience sample; Adults patients undergoing LE fx surgery</p> <p><u>Anesthesia used:</u> not specified</p> <p><u>Inclusion:</u> ≥18 years of age, ANOx3, read/comprehend/write English, admitted for total hip or total knee replacement, patients ability to give informed consent</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> allergies or intolerance to any essential oil in the blend, patient's inability to follow instruction regarding the product</p>		those experiencing PONV as an intervention prior to antiemetic administration.		
(Norton et al., 2022)	Determine the effectiveness of an aromatherapy blend, QueaseEASE, in reducing PONV in pediatric patients in an outpatient pediatric	<p><u>Design:</u> descriptive research design (Iowa Model Revised)</p> <p><u>Setting:</u> suburban pediatric outpatient surgery center</p> <p><u>IV:</u> QueaseEASE (blend of spearmint, peppermint, lavender and ginger essential oils)</p> <p><u>Control group:</u> N/A</p>	<p><u>Sample:</u> N = 31; N = 18 males, N = 13 females, N = 14 orthopedics cases; average BARF scores prior to intervention = 6</p> <p><u>Key Findings:</u> BARF scores decreased in both males and females after the intervention, however,</p>	<p><u>Conclusions:</u> QueaseEASE aromatherapy is effective in decreasing PONV in the pediatric surgical population.</p> <p><u>Limitations:</u> Participants continued to receive antiemetics per the provider's orders. Surrounding irritating odors were not assessed for.</p>	Level II (Polit & Beck, 2018)	Yes, this study shows EBP, as it compared its results to other studies, and used similar guidelines with other studies already conducted in order for results to be

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
	surgical center.	<p><u>DV:</u> Amount of antiemetics used, PONV</p> <p><u>Method of delivering aromatherapy:</u> pod in a foil pack, peel back foil to release scent</p> <p><u>Measurement:</u> BARF (Baxter Animated Retching Faces) score (0-10)</p> <p><u>Sampling:</u> Convenience sample</p> <p><u>Anesthesia used:</u> Not specified</p> <p><u>Inclusion:</u> pediatric patients ages 8-17 years old, English speaking, BARF score ≤ 4</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> history of asthma, allergy to essential oils, unable to follow directions, sensitivity to perfume scents</p>	<p>they were more significantly reduced in the male population (5.8 to 2.1 versus 6.2 to 4.2 in the female population). This study considered a decrease in BARF scores by 2 points as statistically significant, so both groups had statistically significant results. 77.4% of patients that qualified with a BARF score of >4 experienced a decrease in their BARF score by 2 or more points after 5 minutes of aromatherapy. 51.8% of participants that used aromatherapy in the hospital continued using the aromatherapy pod at home.</p>	<p>Non-English speaking patients were excluded due to limitations with the BARF scale (only approved for English speaking patients). Type and duration of surgery were not collected, nor was the anesthesia type, which could affect the level of PONV.</p>		<p>comparable. Since the results were significant, there are increased chances of approval of aromatherapy for the pediatric population across hospitals.</p>

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
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(Rambod et al., 2023)	Determine the effectiveness of lemon essential oil to reduce postoperative nausea and vomiting in lower extremity (LE) fracture (fx) surgery patients.	<p><u>Design:</u> Randomized double-blind clinical trial study; parallel group</p> <p><u>Setting:</u> Orthopedic treatment rooms, OR, and PACU of a science hospital (Iran)</p> <p><u>IV:</u> lemon essential oil</p> <p><u>Control group:</u> Bitter almond oil, which has no scent</p> <p><u>DV:</u> amount of antiemetics used, PONV, incidence of retching, pain</p> <p><u>Method of delivering aromatherapy:</u> drops of essential oil on facemask pre-operatively, cotton with drops of essential oil placed on patient's gown 20 inches from face intraoperatively, cotton with drops of essential oil placed into oxygen mask postoperatively</p> <p><u>Measurement:</u> Pain and PONV was tested using the 1-10 pain scale; PONV was also tested</p>	<p><u>Sample:</u> N=90 patients admitted for LE fx surgery; Control group (N=45); Intervention group (N=45)</p> <p><u>Key Findings:</u> 100% of participants in the intervention group did not vomit, compared to 75.6% of patients in the control group. 0% of the intervention group experienced nausea longer than 1 hour, compared to 31.1% of the control group. 0% of the intervention group received anti-emetics in the recovery room, compared to 8.9% of the control group.</p> <p>The use of opioids vs. nonopioids in the 16 hours postoperatively was the same for both the control and experimental group.</p>	<p><u>Conclusions:</u> Since the amount of pain medications were similar for both groups, lemon essential oil does not seem to have an effect on pain levels. However, since the levels of retching, nausea, vomiting, and antiemetic use was lower in the control group, lemon aromatherapy is effective in decreasing PONV in adult patients who have undergone LE fx surgery. The amount of antiemetics administered to the experimental group receiving the lemon aromatherapy was significantly lower compared to the control group. The incidence of nausea, retching, and vomiting was also significantly lower in the experimental group.</p> <p><u>Limitations:</u> Only one category of</p>	II (Polit & Beck, 2018)	Yes, the type of anesthesia used was discussed, there was a specific surgical subset the aromatherapy was tested on, and the results were significant. The biggest drawback to this study are the specifics – not every patient will be accepting of lemon aromatherapy. However, the specificity makes it evident that for a certain subpopulation of orthopedic surgery patients, a
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Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
		<p>using the Rhodes Index of Nausea, Vomiting, and Retching</p> <p><i>Sampling:</i> Convenience sample; Adults patients undergoing LE fx surgery</p> <p><i>Anesthesia used:</i> spinal, generalized anesthesia</p> <p><i>Inclusion:</i> ability to give informed consent</p> <p><i>Exclusion:</i> sensitivity or allergy to lemon essential oil, PMH of respiratory disorder that could be triggered by aromatherapy, presence of psychological disorder, olfactory or sinus issues, COVID-19 patients, use of adjunct therapy 1 week prior to procedure (aromatherapy, massage, acupuncture)</p>		<p>post-operative procedure was used and it only dealt with lower extremities. Rates of PONV in these types of surgeries may be lower than laparoscopic or gynecological surgeries.</p> <p><i>Notes:</i> Compartment syndrome was also assessed. Lemon aromatherapy made no difference in the incidence of compartment syndrome and thus did not yield relevant results.</p>		<p>specific scent of aromatherapy is effective in reducing PONV and retching.</p>

Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
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(Trandel-Korenchuk et al., 2022)	Determine the effectiveness of inhaled aromatherapy blend to decrease postoperative nausea (PON) in PACU patients.	<p><u>Design:</u> Quality improvement</p> <p><u>Setting:</u> PACU (Northeastern United States)</p> <p><u>IV:</u> Aromatherapy essential oil blend</p> <p><u>Control group:</u> N/A</p> <p><u>DV:</u> Amount of antiemetics used, PON</p> <p><u>Method of delivering aromatherapy:</u> Aroma sticks</p> <p><u>Measurement:</u> Likert nausea scale 1-3 (1=mild, 2=moderate, 3=severe)</p> <p><u>Sampling:</u> Convenience sample; adults in the PACU with PON</p> <p><u>Anesthesia used:</u> General anesthesia, monitored anesthesia</p> <p><u>Inclusion:</u> Patients ≥ 18 years old with post-operative nausea in the PACU</p>	<p><u>Sample:</u> N=36 adult patients in the PACU with PON that used an aroma stick</p> <p><u>Key Findings:</u> 94.4% of patients in the experimental group that experienced PON had a reduction in their nausea by 1 point or more after aromatherapy. 5.9% of patients that did not experience a reduction in nausea received subsequent antiemetic medication. Prior to the intervention, 36.5% of patient cases required antiemetics to be pulled. During the 2-month intervention period, 26% of antiemetics were pulled during the first month, and 21.1% of antiemetics were pulled in the second month.</p>	<p><u>Conclusions:</u> Aromatherapy is effective in decreasing mild to moderate PON and therefore antiemetic use in patients who have received surgery and are in the PACU. All nurses (n = 20) were educated on aroma sticks, and gave patients education on its uses and benefits. Patients stated they liked the ease and autonomy of using an aroma stick.</p> <p><u>Limitations:</u> The essential oils used in the aromatherapy blend were not disclosed. Patients that were too sedated did not use the aroma stick, and there were some discrepancies in charting nausea scores after aroma sticks were given. Dual treatment with antiemetics made it difficult to observe the effect of the aroma stick.</p>	IV (Polit & Beck, 2018)	Yes, this study shows evidence based practice. In order for hospitals to adopt the use of aroma sticks and to determine exclusion, the types of essential oils used will need to be revealed.
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Citation	Purpose	Methods	Results	Implications	Level of Evidence	EBP
		<i>Exclusion:</i> Allergies to inhalation products used, nasal surgeries				